

RM¹ FRAMEWORK

Deliverable 5.2 Data Management Plan

EARMA

Disclaimer: this deliverable has not been reviewed by the European Commission. Its content might therefore change as a result of the review process.

RM Framework project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement number 101188073

Project full title

“Creating a European Framework for Research Management Training and Networking”

Project acronym

RM Framework

Grant Agreement no.

101188073

Deliverable D5.2 Data Management Plan

www.rm-framework.eu

Copyright

 Creative Commons Attribution (CC-BY)

This document is released under the Creative Commons Attribution (CC-BY) license, which allows for the free use, distribution, and adaptation of the work, provided proper attribution is given to the original author(s). By accessing or using this report, you acknowledge and agree to comply with the terms and conditions of the CC-BY license.

For the full text of the license, please visit: <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/legalcode> .

Authors:	Lorenzo Molina
Editors:	Teodora Konach, Blanka Csité
Reviewer(s):	Frank Ziegele, Henning Rickelt, Virág Zsár, João Ramalho-Santos
Dissemination level ¹ :	PU
Submission date:	31 July 2025
Start date of project:	1 February 2025
Duration of the project:	24 months
Organisation name of beneficiary responsible for this deliverable:	EARMA

Document metadata

Version	Date	Modification reason	Modified by
1.0	09.07.2025	First Internal Review	Teodora Konach
2.0	11.07.2025	Second Internal Review	Blanka Csité
3.0	12.07.2025	Third Internal Review	Teodora Konach
4.0	25.07.2025	WP Leaders Review	Frank Ziegele, Henning Rickelt, Virág Zsár, João Ramalho-Santos
5.0	30.07.2025	Final Internal Review	Teodora Konach, Blanka Csité and Lorenzo Molina

¹ Dissemination level:

PU – Public (fully open, automatically posted online on the Project Result platforms);

SE – Sensitive (limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement);

CO – EU classified: EU restricted, EU confidential, EU secret under Decision 2015/444.

Contents

1. Executive Summary	6
2. Introduction.....	7
2.1. Background.....	7
2.2. Structure of the report.....	7
3. Overview of the RM Framework Data.....	8
4. Applicable standards, guidelines and principles.....	8
5. Meeting the FAIR requirements.....	9
5.1. The FAIR Guiding Principles.....	9
5.2. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata.....	10
5.2.1. Making data findable internally.....	10
5.2.2. Making data findable externally.....	10
5.3. Making data openly accessible	10
5.3.1. Open access to scientific publications.....	10
5.3.2. Open access to research data	11
5.4. Making data interoperable	11
5.5. Increasing data re-use.....	11
5.5.1. Re-use of existing data	11
5.5.2. Increasing re-use of RM Framework results.....	12
6. Protection of personal data	12
6.1. Website.....	12
6.2. Social media platforms.....	12
6.3. Events	13
7. Data security.....	13
8. Open Science.....	13
9. ICT Tools and GDPR Compliance.....	14
10. Ethics and Integrity aspects	14
11. Roles and responsibilities.....	14
12. Conclusions.....	15
13. References.....	16
14. Annex	17

Tables and figures

Figure 1: List of Abbreviations

Figure 2: Glossary of terms

Figure 3: The FAIR Guiding Principles (EC 2016)

Table 1: ICT Tools and GDPR compliance

List of Abbreviations

CA	Consortium Agreement
DMP	Data Management Plan
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable
GA	Grant agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
ICT	Information communication technology
OSF	Open science framework
T	Task
WP	Work package

Figure 1: List of Abbreviations

DRAFT

Glossary of terms

Data collection	The process of gathering information or data.
Data management plan	A plan that includes information on the handling of research data during and after the end of the project, what data will be collected, processed and/or generated, which methodology and standards will be applied, whether data will be shared or made open access, and how data will be curated and preserved, including after the end of the project (EC, 2016).
FAIR	Ensuring that data are “findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable” (EC, 2016). The European Commission recommends that Horizon Europe beneficiaries make their research data FAIR.
Metadata	Data that describe other data.
Research data	“Information, in particular facts or numbers, collected to be examined and considered as a basis for reasoning, discussion, or calculation.” (EC, n.d.).
Personal data	“Any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person (‘data subject’); an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person.” (GDPR, 2016, Art. 4(1)).

Figure 2: Glossary of terms

1. Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the data management plan (DMP) for the RM Framework project. It details the RM Framework consortium's plan to manage the production, collection, and processing of its data and publications, during and after the project. It is a living document that will be updated during the project and reviewed by the consortium when necessary or as agreed by the consortium. Each project partner handling and bearing responsibility for data collected, stored, or used in RM Framework will ensure compliance with the strategy outlined herein. This document follows EU guidelines for data management.

This Data Management Plan (DMP) is fully aligned with the objectives and implementation strategy of the RM Framework project. The project aims to develop, test, and validate a European research management (RM) training framework under Work Package 1 (WP1), including the formal aspects of "good practice" training, and to establish a quality label for RM training under Work Package 2 (WP2) set to be applicable across diverse institutional settings. Accordingly, the DMP ensures that all data generated, collected, and processed within the project are managed in line with FAIR principles and Horizon Europe requirements. It supports the integrity, accessibility, and long-term preservation of data, especially those resulting from co-creation activities, pilot testing, and evaluation processes. This enables transparency, reusability, and broad stakeholder engagement throughout the project lifecycle and beyond.

DRAFT

2. Introduction

2.1. Background

The project's Data Management Plan (DMP) (T5.3.1) contains information on the handling of research data during and after the end of the project. It indicates what data will be collected, processed, and/or generated; which methodology and standards will be applied; what – if any – data will be shared or made open access; and how data will be curated and preserved (including after the project's end). The plan will be updated throughout the project lifetime if significant changes arise (e.g., new data or changes in policies or in the consortium). The consortium will be guided by the FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable) Guiding Principles for scientific data management. To facilitate data exchange and re-use, partners will use common, standardised file formats in a consistent manner.

2.2. Structure of the report

This report follows the structure recommended in the European Commission's Horizon 2020, FAIR DMP Guidelines of 26 July 2016 (EC, 2016).

Section 3 (overview of RM Framework data) presents an overview of data that will be collected, processed, and generated in the project. **Section 4 (applicable standards, guidelines, and principles)** covers the applicable standards, guidelines, and principles that RM Framework will follow in the management of its data collection, use, sharing, and preservation.

Section 5 (meeting FAIR requirements) explains how RM Framework will meet the FAIR requirements, as laid out by the FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management. **Section 6 (protection of personal data)** discusses the protection of personal data which is collected and processed in the context of the project. **Section 7 (data security)** covers data security – measures RM Framework partners take to ensure safe and secure data storage and support good security practices. **Section 8 (open science)** addresses the open science commitment of project partners. **Section 9 (ICT tools, GDPR and DPA compliance)** indicates the various information communication tools that will be used in the project and their related policies for GDPR compliance. **Section 10 (ethical aspects)** covers ethical aspects. **Section 11 (roles and responsibilities)** outlines roles and responsibilities of partners, and **Section 12 (conclusion)** concludes the report.

3. Overview of the RM Framework Data

The RM Framework project will generate and manage a diverse range of data throughout its implementation, particularly during the pilot testing and validation phases led under Work Package 3. This data will stem from both newly conducted activities and the analysis of existing initiatives, including ERA Action 17, the RM Roadmap, CARDEA, RITrainPlus, V4WB RMA Network and foRMAtion. These sources offer a robust foundation of policy and project-based evidence, which will be further enriched through the project's co-creation and piloting methodology.

The data collected will encompass both qualitative insights and quantitative feedback obtained through stakeholder consultations, interviews, surveys, pilot implementation results, and workshop discussions. These inputs will inform the development, testing, and refinement of the proposed quality label, handbook and the overall framework. In particular, data will be gathered during the first round of pilot testing with experienced European-level organisations, followed by a second round involving national-level institutions newly engaging with research management practices. Additional data will emerge from outreach activities, online and offline user events, mentoring activities and validation sessions, designed to assess the framework's usability and effectiveness across diverse organisational settings.

All data will be handled in accordance with ethical standards, the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), and relevant national data protection law, with personal information anonymised or pseudonymised as appropriate. Further, Consortium members will be bound by their institutional ethics structures, while in general, the DMP principles are designed with the aim to ensure integrity, quality, and transparency.

Secure storage solutions will be employed to ensure both data protection and long-term accessibility. Findings and datasets suitable for public dissemination will be documented and made available via open-access platforms such as Zenodo, thereby promoting transparency, reuse, and knowledge sharing across the broader European Research Area.

4. Applicable standards, guidelines and principles

The RM Framework project follows the regulations, standards, guidelines and principles listed below in the management of its data collection, use, sharing and preservation:

- European Parliament and the Council, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation or GDPR). This defines key terms, including personal data and pseudonymisation, and sets legal obligations for data controllers;
- European Commission Directorate-General for Research & Innovation, H2020 Programme Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020, Version 3.0, 26 July 2016;
- European Commission, H2020 Programme Guidelines to the Rules on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Open Access to Research Data in Horizon 2020, Version 3.2, 21 March 2017;
- Any national data protection regulation applicable for any of the partners and tasks.
- Research integrity standards, especially the ALLEA European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity.

In addition to the laws and standards listed above, RM Framework will consider and respect the wider understanding of privacy, such as those contained within the European Convention on Human Rights (Article 8), the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights (Articles 7 & 8) and related

case law, and their relation to the security of information technology systems, as outlined within the ISO standard ISO/IEC 29134:2017.

5. Meeting the FAIR requirements

As noted in the Guidelines for Horizon 2020, to which reference is made in Horizon Europe projects, data that are made findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR) can be managed more effectively, and this can foster better science through enabling others to reproduce results and re-use data for future research. In accordance with this guidance, this section outlines how RM Framework fulfils the FAIR principles.

5.1. The FAIR Guiding Principles

The European Commission recommends that Horizon 2020 beneficiaries “make their research data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR), to ensure it is soundly managed” (EC 2016). Based on this guidance, this section outlines how RM Framework operationalises this. The figure below illustrates the FAIR Guiding Principles:

Figure 3: The FAIR Guiding Principles (EC 2016)

Data produced and stored in the context of RM Framework will be made FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable) by following the Data Management Plan (DMP). The RM Framework DMP supports long-term data storage, describes curation strategies where needed, and indicates the metadata used. The impact of RM Framework will be maximised by supporting open access for all produced publications. The RM Framework consortium is committed to the EU’s efforts to improve access to research results and to highlight the positive impacts of public investment in research under the Horizon Europe framework programme. Important results and outputs delivered within RM Framework might be published in high-impact, peer-reviewed open access scientific journals.

5.2. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

5.2.1. Making data findable internally

Internal project documents and administrative data are stored in a centralised, password-protected online repository – SharePoint – owned by EARMA. EARMA is the repository owner and will provide partners with access to the folder and editing rights.

To make data findable and reusable, the following measures are in place:

- **Location:** All documents are stored in relevant folders, organised by WP, in a variety of formats (e.g., Word documents, PDFs, Excel spreadsheets, PowerPoints, or other standard data formats). Partners are responsible for storing documents related to their work on the project in the correct location.
- **Naming of files:** The file names include a short descriptive title of the document and the date of creation or revision, to make them uniquely identifiable and distinguishable (e.g., “D5.2 DMP V01 June 2025”).
- **Reports and documents:** All RM Framework reports and documents contain information on authors and contributors, clear version numbering, dates, and keywords.

EARMA is responsible for curating the internal project data after the end of the project and when the project SharePoint is taken down.

5.2.2. Making data findable externally

The following provisions will ensure that RM Framework outputs are findable externally:

- All public deliverables (in some cases redacted versions) and outputs are published on the relevant page of RM Framework website (<https://rm-framework.eu/deliverables/>) and on the open access repository Zenodo as soon as submitted with the watermark “DRAFT” (unless they are under embargo for publication).
- Zenodo issues a digital object identifier (DOI) to each RM Framework upload to ensure effective and consistent citation.
- The project coordinator will advise all partners of the availability of data and changes to data and their location to facilitate access and wider sharing (as deemed fit).
- Carefully selected keywords will be included with each upload to improve searchability, indexing, and alignment with thematic areas of the project.

5.3. Making data openly accessible

5.3.1. Open access to scientific publications

Each RM Framework beneficiary will ensure open access (free of charge online access for any user) via green or gold open access routes to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results. RM Framework has a dedicated budget for this purpose. As per the GA, beneficiaries shall

- Deposit, as soon as possible and at the latest upon publication, a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication in the Zenodo repository; the beneficiary also aims to deposit at the same time the research data needed to validate the results presented in the deposited scientific publications.
- Ensure open access to the deposited publication – via the Zenodo repository – at the latest:

- a. on publication, if an electronic version is available for free via the publisher, or
- b. within six months of publication (twelve months for publications in the social sciences and humanities) in any other case.
- Ensure open access – via the repository – to the bibliographic metadata that identify the deposited publication. The bibliographic metadata is in a standard format and includes all of the following: (1) the terms “European Union (EU)” and “Horizon Europe”, (2) the name of the action, acronym and grant number, (3) the publication date, (4) length of embargo period if applicable, and (5) a persistent identifier.

5.3.2. Open access to research data

The project will ensure open access to research data via a trusted repository, Zenodo. These data are to be deposited under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public Licence (CC BY) or Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or a licence with equivalent rights.

However, in line with the guiding principle of “as open as possible as closed as necessary”, research data will not be made open access if one of the following factors are applicable:

- It would be against the beneficiary’s legitimate interests, including regarding commercial exploitation; or
- (ii) It would be contrary to any other constraints, in particular the EU competitive interests or the beneficiary’s obligations under the GA.

Before sharing any data, either with the consortium or externally, the partners will ensure that no disclosive information is included.

Public deliverables and outputs (redacted, if needed) are published on the RM Framework website as soon as submitted to the EC (with watermark “pending EC approval”) and without watermark once approved by the EC.

5.4. Making data interoperable

RM Framework partners exchange information using, as appropriate, a variety of means, e.g., e-mail and SharePoint.

To allow for data exchange and re-use between researchers, institutions, organisations, and countries, RM Framework ensures data interoperability through the consistent use of common, standardised file formats. The consortium uses file formats that, even when originating in or primarily used with proprietary software and/or code, are accessible with open-source software. When available and not otherwise in conflict with data security, protection, or processing measures and requirements, the consortium uses open-source software applications.

Through its use of common, standardised file formats and software, RM Framework seeks to facilitate any legitimate and lawful data re-combinations with different datasets from different origins.

5.5. Increasing data re-use

5.5.1. Re-use of existing data

The RM Framework project places a strong emphasis on the responsible re-use of data. Whenever possible, we draw on existing materials — including figures, tables, quotations, and other content — from academic literature, policy documents, grey literature, and press articles relevant to our work. These sources are always properly referenced and acknowledged, with

any necessary permissions obtained for re-use. While re-used data forms the basis of most activities, the project also foresees the collection and analysis of qualitative primary data, particularly in the context of the impact assessment (WP4). Primary data collection will only take place when essential information cannot be sourced from publicly available or existing materials.

5.5.2. Increasing re-use of RM Framework results

The deliverables classified as public will be made publicly accessible via the project website and Zenodo.

A creative commons licence CC-BY (requiring attribution) or CC-0 (no rights reserved) will be used for all project deliverables to ensure that they are shared with minimal restrictions, aside from attribution to the authors or creators. All datasets will include information on methodology, and any data cleaning or transformation steps to support data re-use.

6. Protection of personal data

The project will collect and process personal data only as necessary to carry out project activities, in compliance with the GDPR and relevant national data protection law as outlined above and ethical standards.

To the extent that it is possible, RM Framework partners will make public the data collected under the project. Data will be sufficiently anonymised to ensure that identities cannot be detected. Data will also be formatted so that there is a common set of indicators and a common format for each partner to use to ensure that data is easier to use and reuse.

EARMA is responsible for data management within the project and will ensure that all data collected is securely stored across multiple locations to guarantee both security and recoverability. Work Package 5 (WP5) has tasks specifically dedicated to data management and research ethics and integrity, with associated data storage costs fully accounted for in its budget. All data collection will be carried out with informed consent, including explicit agreement for data sharing and long-term preservation.

6.1. Website

The website facilities are handled by an IT professional at HETFA, with the aim to avoid malfunctioning of the website and keep the website safe from viruses and other malicious software which could compromise the security of data.

In order to ensure the effective functioning and security of the project website, during browsing our websites we automatically collect and store anonymised statistics to keep track of site usage, including log information, the time/date of the visit, internet protocol (IP) address, your device and software information such as browser specifications and operating system. Data collected by the website is not sent to any third parties and is only handled by the website editor and appropriate staff from HETFA. In terms of data storage, the project website cookies have a default expiration time of 2 years.

6.2. Social media platforms

RM Framework uses two main social media platforms, i.e. LinkedIn and Youtube. Each of the platform has their own privacy policy with their own specific terms and conditions, which HÉTFA has no control over. These platforms may collect data generated by users' activity on their own sites and store it using cookies in accordance with their own specific terms and conditions.

6.3. Events

During the project lifetime, in the context of events, third-party platforms will be used for registration purposes such as Eventbrite, Alchemer, etc. Each of the platform has their own privacy policy with their own specific terms and conditions.

The purpose of the registration surfaces is to ensure that those interested in our events can sign up online and provide data necessary for the participation in the event. The registration is subject to the consent. The person agrees to manage their personal data (name, e-mail address, address, title of organisation etc.) to be used for the purposes described above. One may modify or revoke its consent to their data being processed. If one wants to retrieve its consent given earlier, one may look for the person in charge specified for the event. The data provided directly is typically kept until maximum 5 years after the end date of the project. The data is used only for the purpose of the respective project and can be accessed only by appropriate staff.

During the events, photos and videos will be taken for documentation and promotion purposes, a selection of which may be published on our websites, social media channels and in print media.

Participants of the events will be informed in advance if there will be a photographer at the event, thus their consent will be specifically asked prior to the event.

If anyone does not agree on the preparation of photos and videos of them, they have to contact us prior to participating in the event. Photos and videos will be kept for the time that is strictly necessary to achieve the purpose(s) for which they were collected.

7. Data security

All project partners have committed to implementing appropriate technical and organizational measures to ensure data security, in line with the requirements of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and respective institutional and national data management policies. While specific practices may vary by institution, all partners adhere to common minimum standards. At a minimum, data are stored on secure servers, access is restricted to authorized project team members, and all files are password-protected. Each partner has outlined their internal data security protocols at the organizational level to ensure consistent protection of personal and sensitive information throughout the project lifecycle.

8. Open Science

Open Science practices are a core element of RM Framework's methodology and impact strategy, fully aligned with the European Commission's priorities. The project promotes openness, integrity, reproducibility, and early sharing of knowledge. All peer-reviewed scientific publications will be made immediately available through trusted open-access repositories (e.g., Zenodo), under open licences - preferably Creative Commons Attribution (CC-BY). Publication in relevant journals will be encouraged, along with the use of preprints, pre-registration, and registered reports, where applicable.

When disseminating project results, RM Framework will look to publish in relevant journals such as the Journal of Research Management & Administration, Journal of Research Administration, Research Management Review, etc. The project will also aim for 'early and open sharing', as and where appropriate considering relevant exceptions (e.g., journal policies), through means such as pre-registration, registered reports, and pre-prints. Access to data and materials necessary to validate or reuse project results will be ensured in line with the project's Data Management Plan (DMP – D5.2, Month 6).

9. ICT Tools and GDPR Compliance

RM Framework partners will use various information communication technology tools to conduct various activities of the project. The list of identified tools how they are used, and provide information on their GDPR compliance can be found in Table 1 (ICT tools and GDPR Compliance), Annex V.

10. Ethics and Integrity aspects

RM Framework partners comply with Article 14 of the GA which states that all activities must be carried out in compliance with ethical principles. Partners conduct research in accordance with fundamental principles of research integrity, such as those described by ALLEA in its European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity. These principles are reliability, honesty, respect, and accountability (ALLEA 2023, p. 5).

In keeping with the highest standards of research integrity, and to ensure the privacy, safety, and dignity of data subjects, RM Framework partners will provide participants with project information sheets and consent forms in a language and in terms fully understandable to them. These forms describe the aims, methods and implications of the research, the nature of the participation and any benefits or risks (e.g., to privacy) that might be involved.

They explicitly affirm that participation is voluntary and that participants have the right to refuse to participate and to withdraw their participation, or data, at any time, without any consequences. The forms outline how partners collect and protect data during the project (e.g., use of pseudonymisation) and then destroy it or re-use it (with consent). Researchers will ensure that potential participants fully understand the information and do not feel pressured or forced to give consent.

11. Roles and responsibilities

This section establishes the roles and responsibilities for personal data protection in the RM Framework project.

EARMA, as the T5.3.1 lead, is responsible for the preparation of the data management plan and presenting it to the consortium. EARMA will ensure that this deliverable is available in the shared RM Framework repository. EARMA is also responsible for the periodic review and update of this report, with the support of all partners.

All RM Framework partners will provide support and contributions regarding personal data management related to their relevant WPs and project tasks. All partners are responsible for safeguarding the rights and freedoms of data subjects and preventing unauthorised access to personal data and breaches of the principles of confidentiality and privacy. Each partner who collects and processes personal data in RM Framework is responsible for the following:

- Ensuring compliance with the standards and practices outlined in the project DMP (D5.2);
- Ensuring that individuals working on RM Framework have read this document;
- Implementing and adhering to their own organisational and technical measures;
- Informing EARMA of any changes to their personal data collection or processing procedures, including changes in plans for the types of personal data to collect;
- Flagging any concerns about personal data protection as soon as possible so that the issues can be appropriately addressed; and
- Supporting EARMA with the periodic updates of this report in a timely manner.

RM Framework partners will be regularly reminded of the personal data protection measures in place, including during project meetings. All researchers should have the opportunity to raise

questions to gain further information, should it be required. Personal data protection will also form a standing item on the agenda of regular project meetings.

12. Conclusions

This deliverable presented the RM Framework consortium's plan to manage the production, collection and processing of its research data, results and scientific publications. It will be updated and reviewed by the consortium during the project's lifetime and updated in advance of the project's interim review and final review meeting.

Updates will be made to consider new data, changes in consortium policies, and changes in consortium composition and external factors (e.g., new consortium members joining or old members leaving). Each project partner handling and responsible for data collected, stored, or used in RM Framework is responsible for ensuring compliance with the strategy outlined in this document.

DRAFT

13. References

ALLEA (All European Academies) 2023, 'European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity, Revised Edition', June.

<https://www.alleageneralassembly.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/European-Code-of-Conduct-Revised-Edition-2023.pdf>

European Commission (EC) 2022, 'Horizon Europe Programme Guide', Version 2.0, 11 April.

https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/20212027/horizon/guidance/programme-guide_horizon_en.pdf

European Commission Directorate-General for Research & Innovation (EC) 2018a, 'Ethics and data protection', 14 November.

https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/ethics/h2020_hi_ethics-data-protection_en.pdf

European Commission Directorate-General for Research & Innovation (EC) 2018b, 'Ethics in Social Science and Humanities', October.

https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/6_h2020_ethics-soc-science-humanities_en.pdf

European Commission Directorate-General for Research & Innovation, 2016, 'H2020 Programme Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020', Version 3.0, 26 July.

http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf

European Commission Directorate-General for Research & Innovation (EC) n. d., 'Open access and Data Management'. https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/cross-cutting-issues/open-access-dissemination_en.htm

European Commission Directorate-General for Research & Innovation (EC) 2017, 'H2020 Programme Guidelines to the Rules on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Open Access to Research Data in Horizon 2020', Version 3.2, 21 March.

http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-pilot-guide_en.pdf

European Commission Directorate-General for Research & Innovation (EC) n. d., 'Open access and Data Management'. https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/cross-cutting-issues/open-access-dissemination_en.htm

European Parliament and the Council of the European Union, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation), OJ L, 4 May 2016, pp. 1-88.

14. Annex
ICT Tools and GDPR Compliance Table

Tool used	Information on GDPR Compliance	How the tool is used in RM Framework
MS Teams	https://www.microsoft.com/en-gb/privacy/privacystatement	RM Framework consortium uses Teams for its meetings with partners.
LinkedIn	https://it.linkedin.com/legal/privacy/eu?	RM Framework uses LinkedIn to post news about the project and related to the topics covered by the project, to an audience that consists of institutions, organisations, EU projects and individuals that work/are involved in related fields.
SharePoint	https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/answers/questions/1012781/sharepoint-privacy-settings	RM Framework will use this service to assist to store research material to be shared with other partners

Table 1: ICT Tools and GDPR compliance